

THE ROLE OF TOURISM TO DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The tourism sector plays an important role in a wide range of activities aimed at finding optimal ways to develop the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tourism is one of the largest and actively developing sectors of the economy in many countries of the world: the high rate of tourism development, the size of its income has an active impact on various sectors of the economy, which helps the country to form its own tourism industry.*

Keywords: *tourism sector, economy, active impact, tourism industry.*

The tourism sector plays an important role in a wide range of activities aimed at finding optimal ways to develop the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tourism is one of the largest and actively developing sectors of the economy in many countries of the world: the high rate of tourism development, the size of its income has an active impact on various sectors of the economy, which helps the country to form its own tourism industry. The tourism sector accounts for 6% of the world's gross national product, 7% of global investments, one out of every 16 jobs, and 11% of global consumer spending.

Tourism is one of the leading branches of service provision in the economy of Uzbekistan. However, the provision of services is the most important sector of the economy in the market economy. The decrees and decisions adopted by the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the development of the tourism sector directly stimulate the rapid development of tourism.

In recent years, a lot of attention has been paid to the problem of tourism development in Uzbekistan. Recently, the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers are aimed at the development of international tourism and improvement of its infrastructure. Modernization and reconstruction of the material and technical base of tourism has been started due to the active involvement of our republic's own funds and foreign investments. Strengthening of personnel potential of the tourism sector is underway.

However, the analysis of the current state of tourism in our republic shows that despite the fact that Uzbekistan has unique natural, cultural and national opportunities, it occupies one of the lower places in the international tourist business. In particular, the share of tourism in the gross national product of our republic is only 1%. In order for Uzbekistan to rise to the level of world indicators in terms of income from tourism, it is first necessary to improve the system of scientific research in the field of tourism in our republic.

The mechanism of economic activity based on market relations requires the actual reform of tourism enterprises. In the conditions of globalization, the formation of an effective strategy for the activities of these enterprises is an important condition for the existence of the network. Solving global problems requires a large-scale study of strategic marketing and the creation of an effective mechanism for its use both at the state level and among tourism business entities. The need to study strategic marketing in the field of tourism determines the solution of some theoretical and practical issues in the field of marketing activities. Currently, the problems of implementation of activities aimed at increasing the level of competitiveness of the services offered in the tourist

market of the Republic of Uzbekistan by developing a strategic marketing and systematic approach are waiting for their solution.

For this reason, it is important and urgent to develop new approaches to the description and clarification of strategic marketing in the field of tourist services, to create new methods and models describing their manifestation in the conditions of the formation of a market economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The service sector is a rapidly growing branch of the world economy. According to the opinion of international experts, it is noted that the volume of services rendered today exceeds the volume of sales of goods in terms of value. Meeting the growing needs of customers for diverse services is an important task of the service industry and its every enterprise.

Tourism is one of the integral parts of the market of services, and it occupies one of the leading positions in the world economic system: its share in the world gross product volume is about 10%, and its share in the world trade of services is about 30%.

Tourism is the most democratic and international sphere of social activity. Today, it is the only branch of the economy that contributes to the preservation of cultural resources and the environment, to the understanding of their importance for the present and future generations, to the cooperation of the private and public sectors of the economy. The field of tourism determines the attitudes and lifestyles of future generations by facilitating the interaction and interaction of different cultures, creating an opportunity to learn about the past of peoples. Finally, tourism provides an opportunity to actually increase jobs and vacancies. However, many other sectors of the economy reduce them significantly due to innovation.

Currently, the movement of people for tourist purposes covers all countries of the globe. Because of this, contacts between citizens of different countries are becoming a daily reality. Citizens of previously closed societies began to absorb the world especially actively. It is safe to say that international tourism helps to make positive changes in these societies.

Citizens of Uzbekistan have actively joined the process of assimilation of foreign countries that were previously closed to them. The opposite process has also been activated. Uzbekistan is becoming one of the active tourist regions. This situation motivates the rapid development of the hospitality industry and work towards bringing the quality of services to customers closer to world standards.

Uzbekistan sells tourist tours on the international market through advertising of the Great Silk Road, which passed through the cities located in the territory of our republic in ancient times. Because of this, the Tashkent-Samarkand-Bukhara-Urganch-Khiva route, designed for a group of 10-20 people, is a particularly popular tourist route.

A survey of tourist agents selling tours to other countries located on the Great Silk Road (China, Iran, United Arab Emirates, etc.) showed that the prices of tourist products of this country are cheaper than the price of a trip to the Republic of Uzbekistan. Consequently, the growth of tourism revenues in our republic is expected not due to the increase in the price of the tour, but due to the increase in the quality of the provided services. Uzbekistan has the ability to provide any services ordered by tourists. An average of 1200 US dollars comes from each tourist. It is not difficult to calculate the income from this.

The benefits associated with the development of the tourism industry are not only that it provides an opportunity to receive money, especially foreign currency. At the same time, tourism

stimulates the development of many branches of the national economy, construction, trade, agriculture, production of consumer goods, communication.

Tourism is a labor-intensive sector of the economy. Because of this, it plays an important role in providing employment to the population and creating additional jobs. Through its direct and indirect effects, tourism creates a large number of jobs in many sectors of the economy. Determining employment figures in tourism is difficult because only a small percentage of jobs are fully dependent on tourism, whose role is to partially support a large number of jobs in the entire economy, since many sectors of the economy are indirectly involved in the provision of services to tourist flows (for example, food industry, transport, etc.).

Tourism is a good means of creating jobs in areas with natural and cultural-historical attractions. Industrial cities usually do not attract the attention of tourists. The regions of Uzbekistan with great opportunities for tourism development are the places where the industry was not developed in the past (Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva).

Tourism has an indirect effect on the quality of life in these areas by strengthening the level of service provision. This, in turn, attracts entrepreneurs to these areas. They establish their own business in these regions and thus increase the level of employment. An increase in the level of employment allows to reduce spending on social programs after a certain period of time. In addition to the integration of technologies, there will be an increase in the level of knowledge and skills of employees employed in various sectors of the national economy. It has been found that the cost of creating a job in tourism is only 40% of the cost of creating a job in industrial production (latest estimates in Europe). Consequently, the development of tourism can serve as a factor in the development of other sectors of the economy, because the development of this sector is important for the stabilization of the economy of Uzbekistan. The place and role of tourism in the national economy of our republic is determined by the competitive advantages of Uzbekistan in the field of international tourism, the importance of this field in the development of international relations and its contribution to the economic growth of the country.

Figure 1 shows the growth of tourism services in Uzbekistan over the last five years.

Fig 1. Indicators of export of tourism services in Uzbekistan (in millions of US dollars)

When analyzing the income from tourism and the export of tourist services in Uzbekistan, we can see that a steady growth has been achieved from 2010 to 2019. The 2010 indicator of export of tourism services is 121.4 mln. In the case of US dollars, this figure was 214.8 million in 2016,

546.9 million in 2017, 1.04 billion in 2018, 1.313 billion in 2019, and 261 million in 2020. In 2020, it is noted that export indicators have also decreased due to the pandemic that is happening all over the world. WTO reports that the export of tourist services has decreased not only in Uzbekistan, but also in all tourist countries (Figure 1.1).

Studies show that tourism is an important source of foreign exchange for both Uzbekistan and other countries, it helps the development of trade and other branches of industry, as well as the agricultural sector, and provides employment for the population. According to WTO, the tourism industry shows the highest level of growth in cash flow. Table 1.1 shows the dynamics of income from international tourism in the main regions of the world.

The international tourism sector is the fastest growing and most profitable type of business in the world economy by 2020, accounting for 10.4% of world gross domestic product (GDP), 1/10 jobs, 7% of world exports, and 30% of service exports. . In 2019, more than 1,466 million tourists went on international trips around the world, and 1,466 billion dollars were spent on the services provided to them. Earnings in the amount of US dollars. "The number of tourists in 2020 will be 398.3 million due to the sudden outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. per person (74% decrease compared to the previous year), provided services amounted to 536.0 bln. amounted to US dollars (decreased by 75% compared to last year). It can be seen that tourism is currently experiencing a deep crisis, like other sectors of the world economy. It has been estimated that tourism is one of the most affected sectors worldwide.

Table 1

**Income from international tourism in the main regions of the world and their distribution
(in billion US dollars)**

	Changes (%)			Earnings (USD)	
	2019/2018	2018/2019	2022/2011	2021	2022
World	5.0	2.9	-63.6	1,466	536
Europe	4.9	4.3	-59.7	572.2	233.8
Asia and the Pacific region	8.5	1.0	-70.1	441.3	132.6
America	0.4	-0.6	-60.2	322.8	127.1
Africa	2.9	2.1	-63.6	38.9	14.0
Middle East	8.0	19.7	-68.5	90.5	28.7

Source: World Tourism Organization (WTO)

According to the data in Table 1, the average rate of growth of income from international tourism in recent years, during the period before the pandemic, was 3-4%. In 2022, compared to 2021, we can observe that the growth rate of income from international tourism decreased by -63.6% globally, -59.7% in Europe, -70.1% in Asia and the Pacific region, -60.2% in the Americas region, -63.6% in Africa and -68.5% in the Middle East region.

International tourism is one of the three major export industries. In terms of profitability, it ranks third after the oil production industry and the automobile industry³. In economically developed countries, the income from tourism is about 5.5% of the gross domestic product. Tourism is a developing industry in Uzbekistan. Both at the level of state structures and in the

emerging tourism business, research is being conducted to find new forms of work, expand the range of offers and deepen its specialization.

Tourism is manifested in the form of services as a commodity. The set of services together with goods of tourist importance defines the content of the concept of "tourist product". The tourist market is an area where economic relations between producers and consumers of tourist products are manifested. One of the main functions of the tourist market is to realize the value embodied in the tourist product and the consumption value, to organize the process of the tourist product reaching the consumer. The completion of the "money - tourist product" exchange means that the value embodied in the tourist product has been realized and its consumption value has been generally recognized. The function of organizing the process of delivering the tourist product to the consumer, for example, from the tourist firm to the customer, is performed through the system of entities of the tourist services sector.

In the current conditions, the optimal strategy of the commercial activity of a tourist enterprise, which provides a fair distribution of income and expenses in the market of tourist services, creates additional jobs, restores folk crafts and applied art, and allows it to conduct bold and sustainable work, is of particular importance. Taking into account that tourism has a strong cumulative effect on all other sectors, today it is necessary to further develop and improve the tourist complex of our republic, to ensure that it joins the highly developed industry - the international tourist system. All this requires the improvement of legal regulations in the field of tourism.

The government of our republic actively supports the development of international and national tourism and has adopted a large number of legal documents aimed at improving activities in this field. In particular, No. PD-5611 of the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019 "On additional measures for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. PD-5781 dated August 13, 2019 "On measures to further develop the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan", Decree No. PD-6165 dated February 9, 2021 "On measures to further develop domestic and pilgrimage tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", as well as "Additional measure to develop the tourism industry in strict compliance with the requirements of the enhanced sanitary-epidemiological safety regime" dated June 19, 2020 - activities" No. PD-4755 dated July 29, 2022 No. PD-338 "On measures for rapid development of cooperation in the field of tourism with Turkish countries" and "Additional measures on diversification of domestic tourism services" dated April 30, 2022 Presidential Decree PD-232 are directly dedicated to the development of modern tourism. The government of the Republic has adopted several measures aimed at supporting small businesses, including in the field of tourism, in particular, preferential lending, a simplified form of financial reporting, and preferential taxation have been introduced.

The development of the state's efficient economic management mechanism should be based on the analysis of real micro-level production processes in the tourism sector and their correction. This, on the one hand, allows to refocus the attention of state authorities on the problems of tourism, and on the other hand, it helps to support and develop entrepreneurship in the field of tourist services.

The main directions of the state policy in the field of tourism are as follows:

- development of tourism and tourism industry;
- ensuring rest, free movement and other rights of citizens during travel;

- rational use of tourist resources and their preservation;
- improvement of the regulatory framework in the field of tourism;
- attracting investments for the development of the tourist industry;
- creating equal opportunities for business entities in the market of tourist services;
- organization and development of scientific support in the field of tourism;
- personnel training, retraining and improvement of their qualifications;
- development of cooperation with foreign countries and international organizations.

The state policy of Uzbekistan in the field of tourism helps to develop the sector and creates favorable conditions for tourist activity. The main direction of the future activities in the field of tourism is to create favorable conditions for improving the quality of services, to create a modern tourism industry, to promote tourism on a large scale, and to create a unique tourist potential.

Thus, certain measures envisaged by the government of the republic in the field of tourism have a serious impact on the development of the internal structure of the tourist network, the formation of the national tourist industry and raise it to a new level in terms of quality.

It should be noted that, despite the fact that Uzbekistan has great opportunities in the field of tourism, the sector's contribution to the growth of the country's gross domestic product is only 0.4-0.6%. The main reason for this is that the market is not well studied, where the influence of the external business environment is highly variable. Eliminating this shortcoming ensures the competitiveness of the network.

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